

ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BO`LGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. ORTOGONAL KO`PHADLAR.

Quvvatov Behruz Ulug`bek o`g`li

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti

“Umumtexnik fanlar” kafedrası o`qituvchisi

ulugbekovich.bekhruz@mail.ru

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Yangi O`zbekistonimizda yuz berayotgan siyosiy, iqtisodiy, ilmiy – texnikaviy va madaniy o`zgarishlar Oliy ta`lim tizimida ham o`z aksini topmoqda. O`zbekistonda uzluksiz ta`lim – tarbiya tizimini yaratish, shu asosida ta`lim sifatini jahon andozalari darajasiga yetkazish ta`lim sistemasining eng dolzarb vazifasiga aylandi.

Ortogonal kophadlar, matematikada, fizikada, injineriyada va boshqa sohalarda juda muhim bolgan bir tushunchadir. Bu tushuncha, vektorlar toplamining ozaro perpendikulyarlik xususiyatini ifodalaydi. Ortogonal kophadlar tushunchasi, koordinat sistemasidagi bazis vektorlari bolib, ular bir-biriga perpendicular (kophad) ekanligi xususiyatiga ega. Bu tushuncha, koordinat sistemalarda, vektorlar va matritsalarda keng qo`llaniladi.

Ortogonal ko'phadlar, matematikada vektorlarning o'zaro perpendikulyar (to'g'ri burchak bo'lgan) bo'lishini ifodalovchi bir tushunchadir. Koordinat geometriyada, agar uchta vektor (a, b) va (c, d) ortogonal bo'lsa, ularning o'rtasidagi burchak 90 gradusga tengdir. Barcha mantiqiy ko'phadlar, to'g'ri burchakli ikki ko'rinib turgan o'qqa yoki koordinat o'qiga parallel bo'lgan ikki vektordan iborat bo'lishi mumkin.

Matematikada, ortonormal bazisga ega bo'lgan vektorlar ham ortogonal ko'phadlar deb ataladi. Ortonormal bazisga ega bo'lgan vektorlar juda kuchli hisoblanadi, chunki ularning modullari 1 ga teng, va ularning o'rtasidagi burchaklar to'g'ri burchaklardir.

Ortogonal ko'phadlarning xususiyatlari quyidagicha ifodalangan:

Ortogonal ko'phadlar o'zaro moslikka ega emas, ya'ni ular bir hil boshqa vektorlarga teng bo'lmaydi. Ortogonal ko'phadlarning o'rtasidagi burchaklar 90 gradusga tengdir. Ortogonal ko'phadlarning hisoblashida katta qulaylik mavjud. Misol uchun, ortogonal bazisga ega bo'lgan vektorlar orqali kordinatalarni topish juda oson. Ortogonal ko'phadlarning keng foydasi fizikada, matematikada, injeneriyada, kompyuter grafikasida, statistikada va boshqa ko'plab sohalarda

ko'rsatilgan. Ortogonal ko'phadlarning foydasi koordinatlar, vektorlar, matritsalar, fizikaviy modellar, dasturlash, katta datalar analizi va ko'plab boshqa sohalarda ko'rsatiladi. Bu tushuncha, matematikaviy va amaliyotiy o'qitishda, ilmiy tadqiqotlarda va industriyalarda keng qo'llaniladi.

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Ortogonal ko'phadlar matematikaning va raqamli tahlilning ko'plab sohalarida qo'llaniladi. Ular har tomonlama o'rganilgan va ularning ko'pgina xususiyatlari ma'lum. Quyida katta mavzuning juda kichik to'plami keltirilgan.

$\varphi_n(x)$, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ (n ko'phad darajasi) ko'phadlar

$$\int_a^b \omega(x) \varphi_m(x) \varphi_n(x) dx = 0, \quad m \neq n \quad (1)$$

bo'lsa, $\omega(x)$ og'irlik funksiyasiga nisbatan (a, b) oraliqda ortogonal to'plam hosil qilishga yordam beradi.

To'plam, doimiy **omildan** tashqari, vazn funksiyasini tanlash va integral chegaralari bilan aniqlanadi. Ya'ni, ortogonal ko'phadlarning har bir to'plami ma'lum $\omega(x)$, a , va b bilan bog'langan. Doimiy omil standartlashtirish bilan belgilanadi. Mashhur matematiklar nomi bilan atalgan ba'zi klassik ortogonal ko'phadlar 1 – jadvalda keltirilgan. Jadvalning oxirgi ustunida foydalanilgan standartlashtirish ko'rsatilgan.

Name	Symbol	a	b	$\omega(x)$	$\int_a^b \omega(x) [\varphi_n(x)]^2 dx$
Legendre	$P_n(x)$	-1	1	1	$2/(2n+1)$
Chebyshev	$T_n(x)$	-1	1	$(1-x^2)^{-1/2}$	$\pi/2 \quad (n > 0)$
Laguerre	$L_n(x)$	0	∞	e^{-x}	1
Hermite	$H_n(x)$	$-\infty$	∞	e^{-x^2}	$\sqrt{\pi} 2^n n!$

1-jadval. Klassik ortogonal ko'phadlar.

Ortogonal ko'phadlar

$$a_n \varphi_{n+1}(x) = (b_n + c_n x) \varphi_n(x) - d_n \varphi_{n-1}(x) \quad (2)$$

ko'rinishdagi takrorlanish munosabatlariga bo'ysunadi. Agar to'plamning dastlabki ikkita ko'phadlari ma'lum bo'lsa, to'plamning boshqa elementlari ham shunday bo'lishi mumkin. Bu ko'phadlar (2) tenglamadan hisoblab chiqiladi. Takrorlanish formulasidagi koeffitsientlar $\varphi_0(x)$ va $\varphi_1(x)$ bilan birgalikda 2 – jadvalda keltirilgan.

Name	$\varphi_0(x)$	$\varphi_1(x)$	a_n	b_n	c_n	d_n
Legendre	1	x	$n + 1$	0	$2n + 1$	n
Chebyshev	1	x	1	0	2	1
Laguerre	1	$1 - x$	$n + 1$	$2n + 1$	-1	n
Hermite	1	$2x$	1	0	2	2

2 -jadval. Takrorlanish koeffitsientlari

Klassik ortogonal ko'phadlarni ham ushbu formulalardan olish mumkin

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_n(x) &= \frac{(-1)^n}{2^n n!} \frac{d^n}{dx^n} \left[(1-x^2)^n \right] \\
 T_n(x) &= \cos(n \cdot \cos^{-1} x), \quad n > 0 \\
 L_n(x) &= \frac{e^x}{n!} \frac{d^n}{dx^n} (x^n e^{-x})
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

$$H_n(x) = (-1)^n e^{x^2} \frac{d^n}{dx^n} (e^{-x^2})$$

va ularning hosilalarini quyidagidan hisoblash mumkin.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1-x^2) p'_n(x) &= n[-x p_n(x) + p_{n-1}(x)] \\
 (1-x^2) T'_n(x) &= n[-x T_n(x) + n T_{n-1}(x)] \\
 L'_n &= n[L_n(x) - L_{n-1}(x)] \\
 H'_n(x) &= 2n H_{n-1}(x)
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Gauss integrallashiga taalluqli ortogonal ko'phadlarning boshqa xossalari quyidagilardan iborat:

- $\varphi_n(x)$ ning (a, b) oralig'ida n ta haqiqiy, aniq nolga ega.
- $\varphi_n(x)$ ning nollari $\varphi_{n+1}(x)$ ning nollari orasida yotadi.
- n - darajali har qanday ko'phad $P_n(x)$ ko'rinishda ifodalanishi mumkin.

$$P_n(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n c_i \varphi_i(x) \tag{5}$$

- (5) tenglamadan va (1) tenglamadagi ortogonallik xossasidan kelib chiqadiki,

$$\int_a^b \omega(x) P_n(x) \varphi_{n+m}(x) dx = 0, \quad m \geq 0 \tag{6}$$

Tugun absissalar va vaznlarni aniqlash

Teorema: $x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n$ tugun absissalari (1) tenglamada aniqlangan ortogonal to'plamga tegishli bo'lgan $\varphi_{n+1}(x)$ ko'phadining nollaridir.

Isbot: Isbotni $f(x) = P_{2n+1}(x)$ ni $2n+1$ - darajali ko'phad bo'lishiga ruxsat berishdan boshlaymiz, chunki $n+1$ tugunlari bilan Gauss integrallashi ushbu ko'phad uchun aniq bo'lgani uchun bizda

$$\int_a^b \omega(x) P_{2n+1}(x) dx = \sum_{i=0}^n A_i P_{2n+1}(x_i) \quad (7)$$

mayjud.

$2n+1$ darajali ko'phad har doim

$$P_{2n+1}(x) = Q_n(x) + R_n(x)\varphi_{n+1}(x) \quad (8)$$

ko'rinishida yozilishi mumkin.

Bu yerda $Q_n(x)$, $R_n(x)$, va $\varphi_{n+1}(x)$ pastki belgilar bilan ko'rsatilgan darajali ko'phadlardir. Shuning uchun,

$$\int_a^b \omega(x) P_{2n+1}(x) dx = \int_a^b \omega(x) Q_n(x) dx + \int_a^b \omega(x) R_n(x) \varphi_{n+1}(x) dx \quad (9)$$

Ammo (6) tenglamaga ko'ra o'ng tomondagi ikkinchi integral yo'qoladi, shuning uchun,

$$\int_a^b \omega(x) P_{2n+1}(x) dx = \int_a^b \omega(x) Q_n(x) dx \quad (10)$$

$Q_n(x)$ va $R_n(x)$ berilgan $P_{2n+1}(x)$ va $\varphi_{n+1}(x)$ uchun yagona ekanligini ko'rsatish mumkin.

n - darajali ko'phad $n+1$ nuqta bilan yagona aniqlanganligi sababli, A_i ni har doim shunday topish mumkinki

$$\int_a^b \omega(x) Q_n(x) dx = \sum_{i=0}^n A_i Q_n(x_i) \quad (11)$$

(7) tenglamaga kelish uchun x_i tugunli absissalar uchun ildizlarini tanlashimiz kerak. $\varphi_{n+1}(x) = 0$. tenglamaga ko'ra, u holda biz quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz.

$$P_{2n+1}(x_i) = Q_n(x_i), \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, n \quad (12)$$

(10) va (11) tenglamalar bilan birgalikda

$$\int_a^b \omega(x) P_{2n+1}(x) dx = \int_a^b \omega(x) Q_n(x) dx = \sum_{i=0}^n A_i P_{2n+1}(x_i) \quad (13)$$

ga olib keladi.

Teorema.

$$A_i = \int_a^b \omega(x) \ell_i(x) dx, i = 0, 1, \dots, n \quad (14)$$

Bu yerda $\ell_i(x)$ ketma-ketlik $x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n$ tugunlarini qamrab olgan Lagranjning asosiy funksiyalari.

Isbot. Lagranj formulasini $Q_n(x)$ ga qo'llash natijasida

$$Q_n(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n Q_n(x_i) \ell_i(x) \quad (15)$$

hosil bo'ladi, bu tenglama (11) ga almashtirilganda bizga

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \left[Q_n(x_i) \int_a^b \omega(x) \ell_i(x) dx \right] = \sum_{i=0}^n A_i Q_n(x_i) \quad (16)$$

yoki

$$\sum_{i=0}^n Q_n(x_i) \left[A_i - \int_a^b \omega(x) \ell_i(x) dx \right] = 0 \quad (17)$$

ni beradi. Bu tenglama (14) tenglamaga ekvivalent bo'lgan

$$A_i - \int_a^b \omega(x) \ell_i(x) dx = 0, i = 0, 1, \dots, n \quad (18)$$

bo'lgandagina n - darajali ixtiyoriy $Q_n(x)$ uchun bajarilishi mumkin.

4 - bobda ko'rib chiqilgan usullardan biri bo'yicha ortogonal to'plamga tegishli $\varphi_{n+1}(x)$ ko'phadning $x_i, i = 0, 1, \dots, n$ nollarini hisoblash qiyin emas. Nollar ma'lum bo'lgach, $A_i, i = 0, 1, \dots, n$ vaznlarini (14) tenglamadan topish mumkin.

Ammo quyidagi formulalarni hisoblash osonroq:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Gauss - Legendre} \quad A_i &= \frac{2}{(1-x_i^2) \cdot [p'_{n+1}(x_i)]^2} \\ \text{Gauss - Laguerre} \quad A_i &= \frac{1}{x_i [L_{n+1}(x_i)]^2} \\ \text{Gauss - Hermite} \quad A_i &= \frac{2^{n+2} (n+1)! \sqrt{\pi}}{[H'_{n+1}(x_i)]^2} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Klassik Gauss kvadraturalari uchun absissalar va vaznlar

Bu yerda biz ba'zi klassik Gauss integratsiya formulalarini sanab o'tamiz. $N = 1$ dan 5 gacha bo'lgan tugun absissalar va vaznlar jadvallari oltita kasrgacha yaxlitlangan.

Ushbu jadvallar qo'lda hisoblash uchun etarli bo'lishi kerak, ammo dasturlashda sizga aniqroq yoki ko'proq tugunlar kerak bo'lishi mumkin. Bunday holda siz

integratsiya dasturidagi absissalar va vaznlarni hisoblash uchun boshqa manbalarga.³ murojaat qilishingiz yoki pastki dasturdan foydalanishingiz kerak.⁴

$$E = \int_a^b \omega(x) f(x) dx - \sum_{i=0}^n A_i f(x_i) \quad (20)$$

Gauss kvadraturasidagi kesish xatosi $E = K(n)f^{(2n+2)}(c)$, ko`rinishga ega, bu yerda  $E = K(n)f^{(2n+2)}(c)$  ( $c$  ning qiymati noma`lum; faqat uning chegaralari berilgan). $K(n)$ ning ifodasi aniq kvadraturaga bog`liq. Agar  $f(x)$  ning hosilalarini hisoblash mumkin bo`lsa, xato formulalari xato chegaralarini hisoblashda foydalidir.

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